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Wavelength-Stabilized DBR High-Power Diode Laser

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Abstract

This paper reports a wavelength-stabilized High Power Diode Laser emitting up to 14 W CW in the 9xx nm range. Wavelength stabilization is achieved by a Distributed Bragg Reflector (DBR) monolithically integrated in the diode laser chip. Key features are Identical Layer Epitaxy (ILE) and use of a multiple-order Electron Beam Lithography (EBL) optical confining grating. ILE avoids any regrowth or complex technology process, while EBL multiple-order grating allows narrow-band back reflection, effective lateral optical confinement and makes it possible to stabilize multiple wavelengths on the same wafer by a manufacturable and reliable technology. DBR diode lasers with different pitches, whose wavelength were 3 nm spaced, were fabricated and high spectral purity (95 % optical power within about 0.6 nm) and wavelength stability was measured. Moreover, high uniformity of performances across the wafer with different emitted wavelengths demonstrates the maturity of proposed technology for high yield, high volume laser diode production for wavelength stabilized applications. A multi-emitter module including 10 DBR diode lasers, collimating and focusing optics showed 100 W CW, wavelength stabilized output power at 14 A in a 135 μm -core optical fiber within 0.17 NA. Single diode lasers, or multi-emitter modules, can be used to combine high power optical beams by Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) using dichroic optics, scaling up beam power to kW range maintaining optical beam quality.

Keywords: high power diode laser, wavelength stabilization, DBR, Identical Layer Epitaxy

1. Introduction

Wavelength-stabilized high-power diode lasers are key components for many applications, including 976 nm optical pumping of Yb-doped fiber lasers or laser beam combining for high power, high radiance sources exploiting WDM [1-3].

DBR monolithically integrated to the semiconductor diode chip is an attractive, potentially high-yield and low-cost, technology if compared with more common hybrid coupling of Volume Bragg Gratings (VBG) to packaged high-power

Fabry-Perot diode lasers [4]. Many demonstrations of high power Distributed FeedBack (DFB) and DBR diode lasers are reported in literature [5-8]. VBG implies considerable increase of the cost due to the needs of additional components and their adjustment; moreover it is limited by additional losses in the optical cavity and intrinsic sensitivity to mechanical disturbances.

This paper reports a DBR High Power Diode Laser (DBR-HPDL), emitting up to 14 W CW (limited by thermal roll off) in the 9xx nm range. A proprietary shaped DBR [9],

fabricated by EBL and dry etching, constitutes the high-reflection mirror of the diode laser. By changing the grating pitch, multiple stabilized wavelengths on the same wafer are achievable. The shaped DBR includes gratings with different order, and different duty cycle, in the waveguiding region and in the lateral claddings, see Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. This allows narrow-band back reflection as well as effective, and controlled, lateral optical confinement, avoiding additional modal losses in the DBR section. Moreover, the laser structure is identical (ILE) in both the active section and the DBR section avoiding regrowth or quantum well intermixing techniques which could be critical at high power operation. The internal optical pumping induces the required transparency of the DBR section during device operation.

DBR-HPDL wafers with different grating pitches, whose wavelength were 3 nm spaced, were fabricated. High spectral purity, see Fig. 3, and high wavelength stability versus injected current (wavelength shift reduced by a factor of about 5 compared to Fabry Perot lasers) candidates DBR-HPDL as a suitable device for wavelength stabilized pump source, and high brightness.

A statistical analysis of the device performances, including emitted wavelengths, demonstrated high uniformity across a 4" wafer and capability analysis showed high yield for the key parameters. This analysis demonstrated the maturity of the proposed technology, shaped DBR with ILE, for high-yield, highly-manufacturable wavelength-stabilized high-power diode lasers.

A multi-emitter package including 10 DBR-HPDL's, slow-axis and fast-axis collimating lenses, mirrors and focusing lens showed 100 W CW at 14 A, wavelength-stabilized, output beam in a 135 μm core optical fiber within 0.17 NA.

Figure 1 - Shaped DBR grating providing both back-reflection and lateral optical confinement

Figure 2 - SEM top view of the shaped DBR. 1st order grating (waveguide core) is in the upper part while 3rd order grating (lateral cladding) is in the lower part.

Figure 3 - Superimposed spectra (10 A bias) emitted by three DBR HPDL's, obtained from the same wafer, with three different grating pitches

2. Device design

The laser epitaxial structure consists of a single 8 nm InGaAs/AlGaAs Quantum Well (QW) embedded between asymmetric, graded-index, separate confinement heterostructure (GRIN-SCH) AlGaAs layers. GaAs cap, AlGaAs p cladding and AlGaAs n cladding complete the epitaxial structure, see Fig. 4(a).

The QW and the epitaxial layers (thickness, doping, and compositions) were designed and optimized using the software Harold by Photon Design [10]. The modelling drove

an extensive experimental study with successive generations of prototypes fabricated. Fig. 4(b) shows the vertical refractive index profile of the epitaxial heterostructure and the vertical (fast-axis) optical mode.

Figure 4 – (a) Schematic cross section of the diode laser heterostructure showing the ridge width, w . (b) Vertical refractive index profile $n(x)$ and optical mode $|\Psi(x)|^2$. The active layer (QW) position and the effective refractive index n_{eff} are shown.

Low optical propagation loss ($< 0.8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), mainly due to free-carrier absorption control through proper layer doping and heterostructure design, allowed a 5 mm cavity length. Lateral mode confinement was provided by a $130 \mu\text{m}$ wide ridge waveguide structure whose effective index step was $\Delta n_{eff} = n_{eff,core} - n_{eff,clad} \cong 1 \times 10^{-3}$, where $n_{eff,core}$ and $n_{eff,clad}$ are the effective indexes in the core and cladding regions respectively. A DBR was integrated on the rear facet side, providing a reflectance of about 90 %, replacing the standard (for Fabry Perot lasers) high reflectance coating.

Fig. 5 shows the calculated spectral reflectance of the DBR section and Fig. 6 shows a calculation of the fabrication tolerance as a function of grating shape parameters. These calculations were performed using a 1D transfer-matrix modelling tool in the effective index approximation. Despite the apparently critic time control of the grating etching, the wide process window allowed by this design resulted in a high fabrication yield.

Figure 5 - Calculation of the DBR spectral reflectance for a 0.5 mm long, 1st order grating

Figure 6 - Process tolerance: calculation of the DBR peak reflectance as a function of the grating duty cycle and depth (0.5 mm long, 1st order grating)

The broad-area asymmetric GRIN-SCH structure allowed reduced vertical \perp and lateral \parallel far-field, (less than $57^\circ \perp \times 12^\circ \parallel$, full width@1/e²). High slope efficiency ($> 1 \text{ A/W}$), low series resistance ($< 20 \text{ m}\Omega$) and high wall-plug efficiency ($> 60 \%$) were also demonstrated. In order to achieve a high reflectance in a relatively short length, the DBR grating has to be deeply etched starting from the top of the ridge [5]. In our device, the cumbersome deep etch was avoided and the technological process was significantly simplified through the introduction of the shallow etched, shaped DBR.

The shaped DBR was fabricated with EBL in a planar region corresponding to the bottom of the ridge, see schematic diagram in Fig. 7. The lateral grating, having lower effective refractive index, acts as an optical cladding providing a lateral optical confinement of the beam, see Fig. 8. Effective refractive indexes shown in Fig. 8 were calculated by solving the Helmholtz equation for the vertical refractive index profile in the two regions.

Ideally, the lateral confinement could be simply achieved by omitting the lateral grating. However, the EBL writing in wider areas and the loading effect in the semiconductor etching [11] would cause a more complicated and less

controllable technological process. Calculations based on the 1D transfer-matrix method, in the effective index approximation, showed that the optical lateral confinement achievable with reduced-duty-cycle and higher-order grating can be similar to that achieved by standard ridge etching on broad-area waveguides ($\frac{\Delta n_{eff}}{n_{eff,core}} \cong 10^{-4} \div 10^{-3}$) and finely tuned by changing grating structure parameters (grating order, duty cycle, etching depth), see Fig. 9.

Figure 7 - Schematic structure of the DBR-HPDL

Figure 8 – Different effective refractive indexes in core $n_{eff,core}$ and cladding $n_{eff,clad}$. n_{high} and n_{low} represent high and low refractive index of the grating in the two regions.

Figure 9 - Calculation of the optical confinement (a) and of the DBR reflectance at Bragg wavelength (b) as a function of the etching thickness, at different gratings orders, m .

Conventional technology for the DBR section, which needs to be transparent at the wavelength emission of the laser diode, uses a higher-energy-gap material: butt-coupling or quantum-well intermixing techniques are the most widely used technology approaches. However, avoiding epitaxial regrowth or high-temperature annealing in high power laser diodes is of utmost importance for the reduction of extremely critical defects within the active cavity. Moreover, both techniques would imply a significant manufacturing cost increase.

Due to the high optical power density within the laser cavity, none of the above techniques were required in our device. Indeed, the optical beam induces the required transparency in the DBR section, according to modelling results achieved by an iterative numerical tool integrating 1D transfer-matrix, laser rate equations and nonlinear optical properties of the QW, see Fig. 10. The insertion loss penalty due to the residual absorption in the DBR section produces negligible effect, in the very few percent range, on the laser threshold and slope efficiency.

The simplified manufacturing process advantage significantly overcomes this small penalty, which anyway does not prevent to reach the optical power target.

Figure 10 - Calculation of the induced transparency in the DBR section as a function of the injected current into the active region from 0.5 A to 15 A, corresponding to optical power from 0 to about 14 W.

3. Device fabrication

The InGaAs/AlGaAs/GaAs epitaxial heterostructure was grown by MOCVD on an n-doped (100) 2-degree-off 4" GaAs substrate.

130 μm wide broad area ridge waveguides together with planar regions at ridge bottom, corresponding to DBR sections, were fabricated by wet chemical etching, see Fig. 11(a). Then the 500 μm long shaped gratings, forming the DBR sections, were fabricated with EBL in the planar regions, see Fig. 11(b). The adopted solution implies a single etching for the whole DBR section, which provides at the same time high reflectance and lateral optical confinement. The resulting technological fabrication process is significantly simplified.

Different grating pitches can be written in different devices of the same wafer thus allowing the fabrication of DBR-HPDL's emitting at different wavelengths.

We fabricated DBR-HPDL's with three different grating pitches corresponding to three emitted wavelengths spaced by 3 nm on the same 4" wafer.

The technological fabrication process for the DBR section, depicted in Fig. 12, starts with a 200 nm resist layer spun on the whole 4" wafer with ridges and planar regions already defined, see Fig. 12(a). After baking, the resist is directly written with E-beam, see Fig. 12(b). The grating pattern is

automatically divided in fields and properly aligned to the ridge by marker recognition. The grating pitch is finely tuned by the field size definition (around 700 μm^2). The single grating area is smaller than the field, thus stitching errors between fields are avoided.

The E-beam-written resist is then developed and removed up to the semiconductor surface, Fig. 12(c), then RIE-ICP with Ar: Cl_2 : CH_4 gas mixture transfers the DBR geometry to the semiconductor material by deep etching, see Fig. 12(d).

Following RIE plasma cleaning of the surface from resist residuals, Fig. 12(e) a passivation SiN layer is deposited by PECVD technique, see Fig. 12(f).

The wafer process is then completed by contact window definition on the p side, p-metallization, wafer thinning and n-metallization.

SEM cross sections of fabricated 1st order and 3rd order gratings are shown in Fig. 13. Good grating shape has been demonstrated since the optimized writing/etching technological process.

A low reflectance mirror coating of about 2 % is deposited on both laser facets after bar scribing and a proprietary passivation technology is used together with an unpumped current blocking region of 300 μm close to the front laser facet to increase the catastrophic optical mirror damage (COMD) threshold and enable reliable operation at high power. Total length of the fabricated DBR-HPDL is 5.5 mm, including 5.0 mm long active section and 0.5 mm long DBR section.

Figure 11 - Device geometry before (a) and after (b) the DBR fabrication

Figure 12 - Process flow of the DBR fabrication

Figure 13 - SEM cross-section views of multiple order DBR grating: first order (center), third order (lateral)

4. Experimental results

4" wafer, integrating three different pitches, whose wavelengths were spaced by 3 nm, was processed and tested, demonstrating maturity of the technology by statistical data of the main functional characteristics.

Bars with different grating pitches were tested in pulsed conditions ($\tau = 3 \mu\text{s}$ pulse duration, $\delta = 0.1\%$ duty cycle) by a semi-automatic measurement setup, to derive electro-optical characteristics across the wafer and for different grating pitches. The goal was analysing the variability of shaped grating technology across the wafer and verifying uniformity of performances at different wavelengths.

Fig. 14 shows statistical distribution of the threshold current and slope efficiency versus grating pitch, as key indicator of device performances. Box plots are showing 25-75% population for the three different pitches: very limited variation of threshold can be identified, mainly due to the gain peak – Bragg wavelength detuning, and consequent slightly different threshold gain conditions for the three pitches. Good and uniform slope efficiency, close to 1W/A, have been obtained for the three pitches.

Figure 14 - Box plot representation of the threshold current (*top*) and slope efficiency (*bottom*) statistics

A set of single DBR-HPDL's have been also assembled p side down on ceramic carriers (by Gold - Tin hard soldering die attach), obtaining the so-called Chip on Carrier (CoC), necessary for CW tests at high bias – high power conditions.

Low thermal resistance is necessary to ensure low junction temperature at operating conditions, critical to reduce power roll-off at high current, and enhance long-term reliability. To this purpose a copper plated ceramic carrier was properly

designed and used for high power applications, ensuring a thermal resistance of the complete structure (from active junction to the base of the carrier) in the order of 1.5 – 2.0 K/W.

Measurements performed in CW, 25°C on CoC demonstrated power in excess of 14 W, see Fig.15.

Due to epitaxial structure design and fabrication technology a low diode voltage was achieved (about 1.5 V at 20 A), ensuring low power dissipation, decreasing the active junction temperature and strongly contributing to the long-term reliability at operating conditions.

Figure 15 – CW emitted power and wall-plug efficiency (diode voltage in the inset) versus injected current (measured at 25°C)

High purity emitted spectrum and good stability over current are key requirements for a DBR-HPDL. Fig. 16 shows results of emitted spectrum stability versus bias current in the range of 2 to 14 A standard broad-area Fabry Perot lasers usually show more than 10 nm of spectrum occupation, whilst DBR-HPDL has demonstrated a reduction to less than 2 nm, in the same bias range.

Figure 16 - Emitted spectrum at 25°C, 2-14 A CW bias from standard broad area Fabry Perot laser (*top*) and DBR-HPDL (*bottom*)

As already described, DBR-HPDL narrow spectrum enables the possibility of multiple emitted wavelength from the same wafer, by writing multiple pitches. Results of devices with the three different pitches, mentioned in section 3, are reported in Fig. 3. Three emitted wavelengths, 3 nm spaced, were obtained with similar characteristics of emitted power and spectral width.

Having analysed the key parameter statistics and defined preliminary device specs - and therefore production test limits - for a typical high power laser diode application, it was possible to study the process capability, thus the manufacturability of this technology. A preliminary study was based on the slope efficiency, as the key performance indicator. Fig. 17 shows overall distribution and capability analysis for the slope efficiency parameter: a production yield of 98 % was demonstrated, for a lower production test limit (LSL) of 0.8 W/A. More accurate capability analysis will imply a precise definition of the product specifications based on the power required for the specific application; however, the tight distribution is a promising indicator of the maturity of the present technology.

Figure 17 - Capability analysis for slope efficiency, showing 98% yield

Device manufacturability enabled the use of DBR-HPDL in the standard production line assembly of high power multi-emitter modules. 10 DBR-HPDL's were assembled into a module where their beams are spatially multiplexed by collimating lenses and mirrors, see schematic diagram in Fig 18(a). Each single beam is collimated using a Fast Axis Collimating (FAC) lens for the vertical divergence and a Slow Axis Collimating (SAC) lens for the lateral divergence. The collimated beams are then routed by 45° micro-mirrors toward a common fiber lens which focuses all of them into the output fiber core. Each DBR-HPDL, including its FAC, SAC and mirror, is mounted on a different step of a stair fabricated in the module package, thus allowing the different beams to be displaced each other until the focusing lens.

The spatial multiplexing technique is intrinsically incoherent and the output multiplexed beam quality is worsened compared to single DBR-HPDL beams. In particular the output Beam Product Parameter (BPP) increases by a factor of about 10; it is anyway still within the beam quality requirement for optical pumping of Yb-doped fiber laser.

Fabricated multi-emitter modules, Fig. 18(b), showed typical characteristics of 100 W CW; 0.6 nm spectral width, with 95 % of power in 0.17 NA within a 135 μm core/155 μm cladding optical fiber, see Fig. 19.

Fabricating different multi-emitter modules with set of DBR-HPDL's emitting at different wavelengths would allow a spectral combination of their output beams preserving the BPP, thus increasing the brightness of the total combined output beam [1].

Figure 18 – 100W Multi-emitter module with 10 DBR-HPDL's on a stair package. (a) Schematic diagram (b) picture of the fabricated module.

Figure 19 – CW emitted power and slope efficiency versus injected current (25 °C); inset shows the emitted spectrum

5. Conclusions

DBR-HPDL's exploiting multiple-order EBL optical confining gratings have been demonstrated using InGaAs/AlGaAs/GaAs ILE material. Fabricated devices emitted up to 14 W CW in the 920 nm range and demonstrated high spectral purity and wavelength stability versus injected current. EBL grating technology enables multi-wavelength array of diode lasers simply by varying grating pitches along the wafer.

This work demonstrates DBR-HPDL's fabricated on the same 4" wafer, having emitted wavelengths spaced by 3nm and similar electro-optical characteristics. Performance uniformity across the wafer, as well as across different grating

1
2
3 pitches, is a key indicator of a manufacturable and reliable
4 technology. It candidates DBR-HPDL as a suitable device for
5 wavelength stabilized pump source and high brightness
6 applications exploiting Wavelength Division Multiplexing for
7 high power laser beam combining. A multi-emitter module
8 including 10 spatially multiplexed DBR-HPDL's showed
9 100 W CW output optical power in a 135 μm core fiber within
10 0.17 NA.
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18 development.
19

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